

Environmental Pollution- Causes, Consequences and Measures: A Study

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Abstract

Today the major issue before the World Community is the protection of Environment. Environmental Pollution is among the major issues highlighted in many discussion between the Government and Non-Government officials whether in the Developed or Developing Countries. Due to rapid Industrial developments in the last decade, the environment quality has become lower. There is so much man made pollution and environmental degradation that the nightmare ahead is enough jittery to shake us all. In India the situation was worse between 1947 through 1995. According to data collected and environmental assessments studied by World Bank experts, between 1995 through 2010, India has made some of the fastest progressing in addressing its environmental issues and improving its environmental quality in the World. Still, India has a long way to go to reach environmental quality similar to those enjoyed in developed economics. Environmental issues are one of the primary causes of disease health issues and long term livelihood impact for India.

Keywords: Environment, Environmental Pollution.

Meaning of Environment

The dictionary meaning of the word environment is a surrounding, external conditions influencing development or growth of people, animals or plants, living or working conditions etc.

In the beginning the environment of early man consisted of only physical aspects of the planet earth but with the advancement of society man extended his environment through his social, economic and political functions.

Environment consists of three basic components –

- (i) **Abiotic or physical component** – Consists of lithospheric components, hydrospheric component and atmospheric component.
- (ii) **Biotic component** – Comprises plant component, animal component and micro-organism component.
- (iii) **Energy component** – includes solar & geothermal energy.

Meaning of Environmental Pollution

Section 2(c) of Environment Protection Act, 1986 – “Environmental Pollution means the presence in the environment of any environmental pollutant.”

Section 2(b) of Environment Protection Act, 1986 – “Environmental Pollutant means any solid, liquid or gaseous substance present in such concentration as may be, or tend to be, injurious to environment.”

Environmental Pollution is a term that refers to all the ways by which people pollute their surroundings. People pollute the air with gases and smoke, poison the water with chemicals and other substances and damage the soil with too many fertilizers and pesticides. It is one of the most serious problem the humanity is facing today.

Science and technology brought in revolutionary change in human life. Modernization made man’s life more comfortable. But modern industries produce industrial waste and toxic gases which are hazardous to human health. In other words modern man is exposed to air pollution, water pollution etc.

Kinds of Environmental Pollution

Environmental pollution may broadly be classified into (1) Natural Pollution (2) Man-made Pollution.

1. **Natural Pollution** – Environment is polluted often by natural phenomenon such as earthquake, floods, drought, cyclones etc.
2. **Man-made Pollution** – In this type of pollution human activities is included.

The environmental pollution can also be classified further as Air Pollution, Water Pollution, Noise Pollution, Land Pollution, Food Pollution and Radio-active Pollution etc.

Factors of Environmental Problems

The most striking reason of environmental degradation is the rapid rate of exploitation of natural resources, technological development and industrial expansion. Following may be described as the major sources of environmental degradation –

- 1. Deforestation** – No doubt, forests are invaluable property of a nation. But it is a matter of serious concern that the present economic man has forgotten the environmental and ecological significance of natural vegetations mainly forests and has destroyed the forests so rapidly, which has immediate adverse effects on soil and land.
Deforestation gives birth to several problems of environmental degradation.
- 2. Agricultural Development** – Agricultural Development means expansion of agricultural land increase in agricultural land increase in agricultural productivity and net agricultural production. It degrades the environment in a variety of ways e.g. (i) through the application of chemical fertilizers and pesticides and insecticides; (ii) through the increase of irrigation facilities; (iii) by making changes in biological communities etc.
- 3. Population Growth** – Growth of human population at alarming rate is the most significant of the lowering of environmental quality and ecological balance. Over population is the root cause of environmental degradation on and ecological imbalance.
- 4. Industrial Development** – Rapid rate of industrialization resulted into rapid rate of exploitation of natural resources. The adverse effects of industrialization may change the overall character of natural system.
- 5. Urbanization** – Increasing urbanization means increase in the concentration of human population in limited space which results in the increase of buildings, roads and streets sewage and storm drains, vehicles, factories, smoke, dust etc., which causes several environmental problems.
- 6. Poverty** – It is true that poor cause damage to environment. Due to poverty people exploit excessively the natural resources of the country for meeting their basic needs (food, shelter, employment, cattle food). Poverty and need are indeed the greatest polluters as told by Mrs. Indira Gandhi in her address to the Stockholm Conference.
- 7. Modern Productive Technology** -
The development of modern technologies has definitely created most of the present day environmental problems. The Bhopal Gas Tragedy of Dec. 3-4, 1984 is the fittest example of lethal effects of the failure of modern technology. The most dangerous aspect of modern technologies is the problem of disposal of nuclear waste materials coming out of the nuclear reactor plants. Hence necessary steps should be taken to bring the poor people above the poverty line.

Along with these factors, coal burnt thermal power plants, unplanned urbanization, nature of modern technology and increased general affluence and economic growth are some more factors which are responsible for environmental pollution in India.

International Historical Perspective of Environment Protection

- 1. Stockholm Conference, 1972** – The U.N. Conference on the Human Environment held at Stockholm from June 5 to June 16, 1972 to solve the problems of conservation and regulation of human environment by International Agreement on a universal level. The main contribution of the Stockholm Conference of 1972 comprises of –
 - a) The declaration on the Human Environment.
 - b) The action plan for the Human Environment.
 - c) The Resolution on Institutional Financial Arrangements.
 - d) Resolution on Designation of a World Environment Day.
 - e) Resolution on Nuclear Weapons Tests.
 - f) Resolution on the Convening of a Second Conference.
 - g) Decision to refer to Govt. recommendation for action at the national level.

India was also a signatory to the resolutions passed at this conference.

- 2. Earth Summit, 1992** – The Earth Summit or United Nations Conference on Environment and Development (UNCED) was held at Rio De Janeiro, Capital of Brazil from June 3 to 12, 1992. It was attended by 178 nations. It contains 27 principles and enlisting general rights and obligations on

environmental protection. It is for the nations – both developed and the developing to bring it to fruition so as to ensure the world, safe for the present and future generations.

Constitutional and Legislative Measures of Environment Protection

Stockholm Declaration of 1972 was perhaps the first major attempt to conserve and protect the human environment at the international level. As a consequence of this Declaration, the States were required to adopt legislative measures to protect and improve the environment. Accordingly, Indian Parliament inserted two Articles, i.e., 48A and 51A in the Constitution of India in 1976, Article 48A of the Constitution rightly directs that the State shall endeavour to protect and improve the environment and safeguard forests and wildlife of the country.

Similarly, clause (g) of Article 51A imposes a duty on every citizen of India, to protect and improve the natural environment including forests, lakes, river, and wildlife and to have compassion for living creatures. The cumulative effect of Articles 48A and 51A (g) seems to be that the ‘State’ as well as the ‘citizens’ both are new under constitutional obligation to conserve, perceive, protect and improve the environment. Every generation owes a duty to all succeeding generations to develop and conserve the natural resources of the nation in the best possible way. The phrase ‘protect and improve’ appearing in both the Articles 48A and 51A(g) seems to contemplate an affirmative government action to improve the quality of environment and not just to preserve the environment in its degraded form.

Apart from the constitutional mandate to protect and improve the environment, there are a plenty of legislations on the subject but more relevant enactments for our purpose are the Water (Prevention and Control of Pollution) Act, 1974; the Water (Prevention and Control of Pollution) Cess Act, 1977; the Air (Prevention and Control of Pollution) Act, 1981; the Environment (Protection) Act, 1986; Public Liability Insurance Act, 1991; the National Environment Tribunal Act, 1995 and the National Environment Appellate Authority Act, 1997; the Wildlife (Protection) Act, 1972; the Forest (Conservation) Act, 1980.

The Water Act provides for the prevention and control of water pollution and the maintaining or resorting of the wholesomeness of water. The Act prohibits any poisonous, noxious or polluting matter from entering two stream or well. The Act provides for the formation of Central Pollution Control Board and State Pollution Control Board. The new industries are required to obtain prior approval of such Boards before discharging any trade effluent, sewages into water bodies. No person, without the previous consent of the Boards shall bring into use new or altered outlet for the discharge of sewage or trade effluent into a stream or well or sewer or on land. The consent of the Board shall also be required for continuing an existing discharge or sewage or trade effluent into a stream or well or sewer or land.

In the Ganga Water Pollution Case, the owners of some tanneries near Kanpur were discharging their effluents from their factories in Ganga without setting up primary treatment plants. The Supreme Court held that the financial capacity of the tanneries should be considered as irrelevant while requiring them to establish primary treatment plants. The Court directed to stop the running of these tanneries and also not to let out trade effluents from the tanneries either directly or indirectly into the river Ganga without subjecting the trade effluents to a permanent process by setting up primary treatment plants as approved by the State Pollution Control Board.

The Water (Prevention and Control of Pollution) Cess Act, 1977 aims to provide levy and collection of a cess on water consumed by persons carrying certain industries and local authorities to augment the resources of the Central Board and the State Boards constituted for the prevention and control of water pollution. The object is to realise money from those whose activities lead to pollution and who must bear the expenses of the maintaining and running of such Boards. The industries may obtain a rebate as to the extent of 25% if they set up treatment plant of sewage or trade effluent.

The Air Act has been designed to prevent, control and abatement of air pollution. The major sources of air pollution are industries, automobiles, domestic fires, etc. The air pollution adversely affects heart and lung and reacts with hemoglobin in the blood. According to Roggar Mustress, the American Scientist, air pollution causes mental tension which leads to increase in crimes in the society.

The Air Act defines an air pollutant as any ‘solid, liquid or gaseous substance including noise present in the atmosphere in such concentration as may be or tend to be injurious to human beings or other living creatures or plants or property or environment.’ The Act provides that no person shall without the previous consent of the State Board establish or operate any industrial plant in an air-pollution control area. The Central Pollution Control Board and the State Pollution Control Board constituted under the Water Act shall also perform the

power and functions under the Air Act. The main function of the Boards under the Air Act is to improve the quality of air and to prevent, control and abate air pollution in the country.

The permission granted by the Board may be conditional one wherein stipulations are made in respect of raising of stack height and to provide various control equipments and monitoring equipments. It is expressly provided that persons carrying on industry shall not allow emission of air pollutant in excess of standards laid down by the Board.

In Delhi, the public transport system including buses and taxis are operating on a single fuel CNG mode on the directions given by the Supreme Court. Initially, there was a lot of resistance from bus and taxi operators. But now they themselves realise that the use of CNG is not only environment friendly but also economical.

Noise has been taken as air pollutant within the meaning of Air Act, Sound becomes noise when it causes annoyance or irritates. There are many sources of noise pollution like factories, vehicles, reckless use of loudspeakers in marriages, religious ceremonies, religious places, etc. Use of crackers on festivals, winning of teams in the games, and other such occasions causes not only noise pollution but also air pollution. The Air Act prevents and controls both these pollutions.

The Environment (Protection) Act, 1986 was enacted to provide for the protection and improvement of the quality of environment and preventing, controlling and abating environmental pollution. The Act came into existence as a direct consequence of the Bhopal Gas Tragedy. The term 'environment' has been defined to include water, air and land, and the inter-relationship which exists among and between water, air and land and human beings, other living creatures, plants, micro-organism and property. The definition is wide enough to include within its purview all living creatures including plants and micro-organism and their relationship with water, air and land. The Act has given vast powers to the Central Government to take measures with respect of planning and execution of a nation-wise programme for prevention, control and abatement of environmental pollution. It empowers the Government to lay down standards for the quality of environment, emission or discharge of environmental pollutants; to regulate industrial locations; to prescribe procedure for managing hazardous substances, to establish safeguards for preventing accidents; and to collect and disseminate information regarding environmental pollution. Any contravention of the provisions of the Act, rules, orders or directions made there under is punishable with imprisonment for a term which may extend to five years or with fine upto one lakh rupees or with both. The Act is an 'umbrella' legislation designed to provide a frame work for Central Government coordination of the activities of various Central and State authorities established under previous laws, such as the Water Act and the Air Act.

The Parliament passed the Public Liability Insurance Act, 1991 to provide for public liability insurance for the purpose of providing immediate relief to the persons affected by accident occurring while handling any hazardous substance and for matters connected therewith. The Act provides for mandatory public liability insurance for installations handling any hazardous substance to provide minimum relief to the victims (other than workers) through the mechanism of collector's decision. Such an insurance will be based on the principle of 'no fault' liability as it is limited to only relief on a limited scale. Such insurance apart from safeguarding the interests of the victims of accidents would also provide cover and enable the industry to discharge its liability to settle large claims arising out of major accidents. However, availability of immediate relief under this law would not prevent the victims to go to Courts for claiming large compensation.

The National Environment Tribunal Act, 1995 was enacted to provide for strict liability for damages arising out of any accident occurring while handling any hazardous substance. The Act provides for establishment of a National Environment Tribunal for effective and expeditious disposal of cases arising from such accident. It imposes liability on the owner of an enterprise to pay compensation in case of death or injury to any person; or damage to any property or environment resulted from an accident. The accident must have occurred while handling any hazardous substance. A claimant may also make an application before the Tribunal for such relief as is provided in the Public Liability Insurance Act, 1991.

The National Environment Appellate Authority Act, 1997 has been enacted to provide for the establishment of a National Environment Appellate Authority to hear appeals with respect to restriction of areas in which any industries, operations or processes shall not be carried out or shall be carried out subject to certain safeguard under the Environment (Protection) Act, 1986. After the establishment of the Authority, no Civil Court or other authority shall have jurisdiction to entertain an appeal on matters on which the Authority is so empowered under the Act. It is evident that this Act has been made with objective to provide speedy justice on environmental issues.

The Wild Life (Protection) Act, 1972 was enacted with a view to provide for the protection of wild animals, birds and plants. The Act prohibits hunting of animals and birds as specified in the schedules. The Act also prohibits picking, uprooting, damaging, destroying etc. any specified plant from any forest. The Act provides for State Wildlife Advisory Board to advise the State Government in formulation of the policy for protection and conservation of the wildlife and specified plants; and in selection of areas to be declared as Sanctuaries, National parks, etc. The Act is administered by a Director of Wildlife Preservation with Assistant Directors; and a Chief Wildlife Warden with other Wardens and their staff.

The Forest (Conservation) Act, 1986 was passed with a view to check deforestation of forests. The Act provides that no destruction of forests or use of forest land for non-forest purposes can be permitted without the previous approval of the Central Government. The conservation of forests includes not only preservation and protection of existing forests but also re-afforestation. Reafforestation should go on to replace the vanishing forests. It is a continuous and integrated process. The Act is intended to save a laudable purpose and it must be enforced strictly for the benefit of the general public.

It is evidently clear that there is no dearth of legislations on environment protection in India. But the enforcement of these legislations has been far from satisfactory. What is needed is the effective and efficient enforcement of the constitutional mandate and the other environmental legislations.

Administrative Structure

The Water Act and the Air Act are administered by the Central and State Governments and the Central Pollution Control Board and the State Pollution Control Board. The Boards have been vested with powers to issue any direction including the direction to order closure or stoppage of the supply of electricity, water or any other service to the polluting unit. It may be noted that similar powers are vested to the Central Government under the Environment (Protection) Act.

Further, under the Environment (Protection) Act, the Central Government has framed the Environment (Protection) Rules, 1986 laying down standards for the emission or discharge of environmental pollutants with respect to some major industries. There are some other agencies also framing the standards, namely-Central Pollution Control Board, State Pollution Control Board, Bureau of Indian Standard and Local Authorities, i.e., Municipal Corporation. Apparently, there is multiplicity of pollution control standards for the same type of industries. However, under the Environment (Protection) Act, 1986, the power has been conferred upon the Central Government to lay down the standards of quality of air, water, soil, etc. It is hoped that this will ensure uniformity of standards through out the country. Further, many of the standards have not yet been laid down as stipulated under the respective Pollution Control Acts, may be due to non-availability of instrument to measure the parameters of pollution. This will adversely affect the process of enforcement of laws.

Judicial Contribution

The right of a person to pollution free environment is a part of basic jurisprudence of the land. Article 21 of the Constitution of India guarantees a fundamental right to life and personal liberty. The Supreme Court has interpreted the right to life and personal liberty to include the right to wholesome environment. The Court through its various judgments has held that the mandate of right to life includes right to clean environment, drinking-water and pollution-free atmosphere.

Taj Mahal Case

In Taj Mahal's Case, the Supreme Court issued directions that coal and coke based industries in Taj Trapezium (TTZ) which were damaging Taj should either change over to natural gas or to be relocated outside TTZ. Again the Supreme Court directed to protect the plants planted around Taj by the Forest Department as under: The Divisional Forest Officer, Agra is directed to take immediate steps for seeing that water is supplied to the plants.... The Union Government is directed to release the funds immediately without waiting for receipt of the proposal from the U.P. Government on the basis of the copy of the report. Funding may be subsequently settled with the U.P. Government, but in any set of circumstances for want of funds the officer is directed to see that plants do not wither away.

Dehradun Valley Case

In that case, carrying haphazard and dangerous limestone quarrying in the Mussorie Hill range of the Himalaya, mines blasting out the hills with dynamite, extracting limestone from thousands of acres had upset the hydrological system of the valley. The Supreme Court ordered the closing of limestone quarrying in the hills and observed : This would undoubtedly cause hardship to them, but it is a price that has to be paid for protecting and safeguarding the right of the people to live in healthy environment with minimal disturbance of ecological balance.....

Smoking in Public Places

In 2001, the Supreme Court of India imposed ban on smoking of tobacco in public places all over the country. Smoking causes harm not only to the smokers but also to non-smokers who are forced to inhale the second hand smoke. More than 3 million people die every year in India as a result of smoking tobacco including bidis and cigarettes. One lakh Indians get lung cancer every year because of smoking. Indeed, lung cancer kills 95% of its victims. That is why the apex Court ruling has immense social value. But no one cares for the ban. As you know the cigarettes and bidis are openly sold in tobacco-free railway stations, bus stands, cinema houses, etc.

Pollution in Delhi

In *Almitra H. Patel V. Union of India*, the Supreme Court reiterated the observations made in *Wadehra's case* – Historic city of Delhi, the Capital of India, is one of the most polluted cities in the world. The authorities, responsible for pollution control and environment protection have not been able to provide clean and healthy environment to the residents of Delhi. The ambient air is so much polluted that it is difficult to breathe. More and more Delhites are suffering from respiratory diseases and throat infections. River Yamuna – the main source of drinking water supply – is the free dumping place for untreated sewerage and industrial waste. Apart from air and water pollution, the city is virtually an open dustbin. Garbage strewn all over Delhi is a common sight. The Court directed the authorities to take immediate necessary steps to control pollution and protect the environment.

Environment Court

We have noticed that in the past few years there is an increasing trend to the number of cases based on environmental pollution, ecological destruction and conflicts over natural resources coming up before the Courts. In most of these cases there is need for natural scientific expertise as an essential input to inform judicial decision-making. These cases require expertise at a high level of scientific and technical sophistication. The experience shows that the prosecution launched in ordinary Criminal Courts under the provisions of the Water Act, Air Act and the Environment (Protection) Act never reach their conclusion either because of the work load in these Courts or never reach their conclusion or because there is no proper appreciation of the significance of the environment matters on the part of those in charge of conducting of those cases. It is, therefore, absolutely essential to set up a separate machinery to cut down the delays which are hindering the implementation of environmental laws. It is, therefore, submitted that the provisions be made for the establishment of the Environment Courts with one judge and two experts from the ecological and other sciences. To begin with, we may have a two-tier system one at the State level and the other at the National level which may later be extended even at the District level. Such Courts may be vested with the jurisdiction to decide both criminal prosecution cases under the various environmental laws and civil cases for compensation to victims of any activity leading to environmental damage or pollution. These Courts should be allowed to adopt summary proceedings for speedy disposal of the cases. The appeal from decision of the State Environment Courts may be preferred to the National Environment Court and appeal from the decision of the National Environment Court to the Supreme Court. The provisions should be confined to single appeal.

Conclusion

The causes for environmental problems are many. The multiplicity of causes makes it difficult to clearly delineate the causes and consequences of environmental degradation in terms of simple one to one relationship. The causes and effects are often interwoven in complex web of social, technological, environmental and political factors. However, some of the very common causes environmental degradation which can be clearly pointed out are the population growth, poverty, urbanization, agriculture growth. The process of development itself also leads to damage of the environment, if not properly managed. However there are so many measures for saving environment on national as well as international level. Environment protection is also guarantee under Article 48 A and 51-A(G) of the Constitution.

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